

Functionalized Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs) for reversible gas storage and sequestration applications

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Abstract : The decreasing amount of fossil fuels and increasing threat of global warming from the pollutants have driven the search for clean energy source. Energy sources from fossil fuels still remain in the forefront despite being a major source of increased CO₂ content in the atmosphere. Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs) have emerged as promising materials for hydrogen storage and CO₂ sequestration. Several factors influencing the hydrogen uptake of porous MOFs such as surface area, catenation, ligand functionalization, doping with alkali metals and unsaturated metal centers have been extensively studied. Similarly, well defined periodicity and tunable pore sizes along with less basic amino-functionalized MOFs enables them favorable for fast and reversible CO₂ gas adsorption at low partial pressure and room temperature. In this review we present diverse aspects of metal organic frameworks like fluorination, amino functionalization for high hydrogen storage and CO₂ sequestration capabilities.

Keywords : Metal-organic framework, structural isomerism, fluorination, hydrogen storage, CO₂ adsorption, carbon capture.

Introduction

The decreasing amount of fossil fuels and increasing threat of global warming from the pollutants have driven the search for clean energy source. Although Department of Energy (DOE) has launched the Hydrogen Fuel Initiative project, the commercialization of hydrogen powered vehicles still remains a challenge as it is difficult to create a technology for on board hydrogen storage¹. As a result, energy sources from fossil fuels still remains in the forefront despite being a major source of increased CO₂ content in the atmosphere. Due to these reasons, the capture and storage of CO₂ emitted from coal fired power plants and vehicle exhausts has also emerged as another major research area. The currently employed carbon capture method from flue gas involves alkanolamine based solvents that act as CO₂ absorber by formation of N-C bonded carbamate species. Amine regeneration requires cleavage of this covalent bond by heating (at 100 to 150 °C) and has high operational cost. Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs) have emerged as promising materials for hydrogen storage and CO₂ sequestration². Several factors influencing the hydrogen uptake of porous MOFs such as

surface area, catenation, ligand functionalization, doping with alkali metals and unsaturated metal centers have been extensively studied. In other efforts, CO₂ uptake in amine-functionalized porous solids like zeolitic materials, mesoporous silica, porous carbon, etc. has also been tried. As these materials have the lack of order, large voids, flexible amine groups, and random adsorption sites, the CO₂ adsorption is unfeasible. In contrary, well defined periodicity and tunable pore sizes along with less basic amino-functionalized MOFs enables them favorable for fast and reversible CO₂ gas adsorption at low partial pressure and room temperature³. In previous reports by Yaghi, Rosi, Shimizu and us showed that amino functionalized MOFs can perform better for selective and reversible CO₂ adsorption at very low heat of adsorption range⁴.

Fluorinated Metal Organic Frameworks (F-MOFs) for hydrogen storage : We have been investigating methods to synthesize porous hybrids with altered surface chemistries, specifically perfluorinated surfaces, in order to determine the differences in adsorptive behavior in these materials⁵. Theoretical calculations on fluorinated analogs of hybrids performed have indicated the higher po-

larizability of fluorine atoms results in an increased interaction between the hybrid surface and hydrogen molecules. There are a number of reports of hybrid materials containing fluorinated organic ligands have an interesting hysteretic adsorption/desorption curve, which supports theory whereby H₂ can be loaded at high pressures but then stored at lower pressures. Relatively little success has come from efforts to synthesize hybrid materials containing only metal cations and perfluorinated carboxylates. We have therefore chosen to target structures containing these ligands in combination with other small ligands that are easily incorporated into hybrid structures, such as 4,4'-(hexafluoroisopropylidene)bis(benzoic acid). The inclusion of second ligands i.e. co-ligand assists in forming structures containing the fluorinated ligand and also helps reduce the rather significant increase in density that arises from replacing hydrogen atoms with fluorine atoms. Although several ligands (Fig. 1) have been used for synthesis of diverse variety of partially fluorinated MOFs, among these ligands we have selected the

4,4'-(hexafluoroisopropylidene)bis(benzoic acid) because (a) bent structure of it results into the formation of nano channels into resulting framework, (b) ditopic and highly reactive nature of this ligand towards transition metals may give rise to helical conformation into resulting framework, (c) as it contains the central C atom in sp³ hybridization state, it may give rise to unusual network topologies and (d) long molecular structure of it may result into the formation of microporous co-ordination framework for gas adsorption. As mentioned earlier, in our laboratory we have been synthesized several partially fluorinated MOFs, using the 4,4'-(hexafluoroisopropylidene)-bis(benzoic acid) and co-ligands as phenanthroline, 3-picolin, 2,2'-bipyridine and neocuprine along with transition metals like Co²⁺, Cu²⁺, Mn²⁺ and Zn²⁺. These F-MOFs have been synthesized using solvothermal as well as hydrothermal synthesis procedures⁶.

Among all of these structures, we selected F-MOF-4 and F-MOF-6 for the adsorption studies as they are porous and 2 dimensional and 3 dimensional respectively. The permanent porosity of F-MOF-4 was confirmed by

Fig. 1. MOFs with fluorinated organic links or F-MOFs.

crystal structure obtained from single crystal X-ray diffraction and the N₂ adsorption done on them after removing the guest solvent from framework. Hydrogen adsorption isotherm for F-MOF-4 was studied at 77 K up to 1 atm pressure. The sample of F-MOF-4 was prepared by a thorough washing of crystals with CHCl₃ followed by evacuation at 120 °C for 3 h. While the volume of hydrogen adsorbed by F-MOF-4 is rather modest (0.6 wt% H₂), but this report once again proves that hybrid materials containing a per-fluorinated ligand can emerge as a hydrogen storage materials. There are few reports available previously on partially fluorinated F-MOFs, where researchers have been studied H₂ adsorption at low and high pressure and temperature at 77 K. From these structures and gas adsorption properties, it is clear that not only fluorinated ligands are good for synthesis of partially fluorinated MOFs but also they are promising for hydrogen adsorption. But in the synthesis of MOFs by using fluorinated ligands, incorporation of co-ligand i.e. simple, non-fluorinated, nitrogen containing molecules is necessary to improve the crystallinity and dimensions of the resulting material.

Light weight metal organic frameworks for high hydrogen storage capacity : The light weight MOFs formed by light main group metals such as Mg²⁺, Al³⁺ and Ca²⁺⁷. The light weight MOFs exhibit promising hydrogen storage capacities, owing to their low framework density, high specific surface area, and tunable surface structures onto which hydrogen molecules can be adsorbed. The main group metal cations such as Li²⁺, Na⁺ can also form MOFs but the mono valent cations will most likely produce frameworks that are susceptible to hydrolysis, the large polarizing power of Mg²⁺ and Al³⁺ should give rise to relatively strong coordination bonds. Oxophilicity and predominantly octahedral coordination are well-known characteristics of the two cations, and novel solvent systems will probably need to be employed to avoid formation of dense oxide/hydroxide phases. We also produced a rare porous magnesium based metal-organic framework, Mg-MOF-1 [Mg(3,5-PDC)(H₂O)] (Fig. 2). This chiral MOF (space group P6₁22) is constructed by helical assembly of Mg²⁺ ions with achiral 3,5-pyridine dicarboxylates. Open Mg metal sites show selective hydrogen (H₂) adsorption (*ca.* 0.8 wt% at 77 K) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) uptake (1 mmol g⁻¹ at 298 K) over nitrogen at 1 atm⁸.

Amino Functionalized Metal Organic Frameworks with high capacity for storage of carbon dioxide : Selective carbon dioxide capture from coal-fired power plant is a critical issue as these plants produce post-combustion flue gases with ~15% CO₂ concentration⁹. At present, the separation of CO₂ from such a low pressure stream of gases is performed by amine sorbents through chemisorptions. Recently, ZIFs/ZMOFs, that mimic the zeolite type structure but possess larger and more modifiable pores, has received considerable attention as materials for strategic gases such as CO₂ sorbents¹⁰. However still there is a necessity of new Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs) which will exhibit high adsorption capacity, fast CO₂ adsorption and desorption, and low energy requirement for recycling. In order to achieve that, a number of feasible avenues for increasing the adsorption capacity of such materials, for instance, ion-exchange, introduction of open metal sites, and the use of ligand molecules with specific functionalities (like -OH or -NH₂) have been attempted. Recent theoretical work on the interaction of CO₂ with functionalized aromatic molecules has shown the effectiveness of introducing specific polar substituent groups, e.g. -OH or -NH₂, on the aromatic ligand in increasing the CO₂-ligand affinity. While the ability of ZIFs/ZMOFs to act as materials for CO₂, and H₂ sorbents and NH₂-functionalization of MOFs to enhance CO₂ adsorption has been described in the literature, still there are no reports of a -NH₂ functionalized zeolitic MOF with tetrahedral network topologies as the synthesis of such materials has proven to be very challenging. We also prepared amino functionalized MOF ZTF-1 (Zeolitic Tetrazolate Framework) by the reaction of Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O with 5-amino tetrazole (5-AT) in a *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) solution in the presence of *N,N*-dimethylformamide-azine-dihydrochloride (DMAz) in 3 : 2 : 1 mol ratio at 100 °C for 72 h. This is the first report of a -NH₂ functionalized MOF among different metal imidazoles/triazoles/tetrazoles where only N1 and N4 are coordinated to tetrahedral metal centers with M-L-M angle is close to 145°¹¹.

The crystal structure of ZTF-1 where examined by XRD techniques and the structure was found to be related to the diamond (*dia*) topology (Fig. 3c). Fig. 3b shows the separate adamantane type cage in the structure of ZIF-1. The adamentene cage consists of 10 Zn ions and

Fig. 2. A rare porous chiral Mg based MOF, Mg-MOF-1, containing open Mg metal sites was synthesized which show selective H₂ and CO₂ adsorption over N₂.

Fig. 3. Crystal structure of ZTF-1. (a) The Zn-TET-Zn bridging angle in ZTF-1. (b) Zn^{II} and 5-amino tetrazolate clusters are bridged together to generate an extended 3D porous structure with channels along the crystallographic *c* direction. The framework adopts a *dia* topology. (c) Cage constituents of the *dia* topology. The structure is shown as an exploded tiling of adamantane (brown) with all the tetrahedral Zn^{II} atoms (green) are linked. (d) 3D packing diagram of ZTF-1 [Zn^{II}, blue; C, black; N, green. H atoms have been omitted for clarity].

Fig. 4. Gas adsorption isotherms of ZTF-1. (a) Nitrogen adsorption isotherm 77 K. (b) Adsorption isotherms for CO₂ (circles) and N₂ (triangles) at 273 (red) and 298 K (black). (c) Hydrogen adsorption isotherms at 77 K. The filled and open circles represent adsorption and desorption, respectively.

125-AT and each cage is surrounded 6 similar cages. Note that, because of the way the 5-AT linkers are oriented, there are six 5-AT links pointing inwards each cage while six are pointing outwards. Apart from the -NH₂ functionality, uncoordinated N₂ and N₃ nitrogen are exposed to the pore. As shown in Fig. 1b, the largest 6-membered ring has a pore aperture of 4.3 Å. The architectural stability and permanent porosity of ZTF-1 were also confirmed by measuring the N₂ gas adsorption of the guest-free material (Fig. 4a). The BET and Langmuir surface area were calculated to be 355.3 and 443.8 m² g⁻¹. Fig. 4b and 4c shows the CO₂ and H₂ adsorption isotherms for ZTF-1, which shows a disproportionately high affinity and capacity for CO₂ (5.6 mmol/g at 273 K) than N₂. The CO₂ uptake at 760 Torr for ZTF-1 is 10 times higher than N₂ at 273 K.

Conclusion : In this review, we have presented diverse aspects of metal organic frameworks like fluorination, amino functionalization for high hydrogen storage and CO₂ sequestration capabilities. These MOFs are highly porous and shows the high adsorption capacity for N₂, H₂ and CO₂ at 1 atm pressure. Here, direct comparison between iso-structural partially fluorinated Cu-TBA-2F and non-fluorinated Cu-TBA-2 suggested that, enhancement of H₂ adsorption due to fluorination in MOFs is not an universal phenomenon, but it is rather system specific and can differ from system to system. Similarly, it is hard to quantify the exact contributions of exposed NH₂ functionality or free tetrazole nitrogen for the high CO₂ capacity of ZTF-1 but these results point toward the value of utilizing amino functionalized links and free aromatic

nitrogen atoms as a building block for constructing MOFs for high and reversible CO₂ capture. Nevertheless, thorough research work is necessary on H₂ adsorption on fluorinated and amino functionalized MOFs before we can conclusively indicate positive/negative effect of fluorination on enhancement of hydrogen adsorption in MOFs.

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